

GRAPE PLANT INFORMATION. GRAPES HEALTH BENEFITS.**Nuraliyeva Farangiz Baxtiyor qizi**

Guliston davlat universiteti

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Abstract: The article discusses the main properties of grapes and its effects on the human body. A systematic modern review of specialized literature and current scientific data has been carried out. The specified chemical composition and nutritional value of berries, consideration of the use in various types of the drug and the effectiveness of its use in various diseases. A special analysis has been analyzed with reliable effects of grape exposure on the human body in certain conditions and diseases.

Key words: grape, health, heart, vitamin, variety, benefit.

Grapevines belong to Vitaceae family, while the most commonly used varieties belong to *Vitis vinifera* species (European vine). Other *Euvitis* subspecies are used as rootstocks in areas with extended Phylloxera problem.

Grapevine is a perennial plant bush, characterized by helices – tendrils and trailing growth. It is a climbing plant and normally climbs on rocks or tree trunks. Tendrils grow on stems and are believed to be degenerated inflorescences. Leaves are big, opposite, heart resembled, and inflorescences grow across them. They may be terraced or lobed with 3-5 lobes and distinct nerves. The shape, size and color of leaves depend on the variety.

Buds are located on plant knees between axles, and are distinguished in 2 categories:

Primary (Winter) and Secondary Buds

During spring, we may observe a distinct swelling between stem and petiole. These are the secondary buds. Those are not normally going to sprout during the current growing period. They will most probably stay in lethargy. Next to this bud, there is the primary bud, which is normally going to sprout during the current growing period. In case the primary bud is damaged, usually because of winter frosts (primary bud necrosis), then the secondary bud is going to sprout. Buds give shoots which become canes when they mature.

Shoots produce the flower clusters right after sprouting. Flowers on clusters are small 3-4mm (0,12-0.16 inches) and white in color. Normal flowers are hermaphrodite. These flowers are fertilized and produce grape clusters. Grapes account for the vast majority (90-98%) of the cluster's weight.

Grapes botanically are berries. The size and the color of grapes vary among different varieties. The color, which may vary from green to deep red, is a result of the grape content in anthocyanins and flavonoids. This content is basically affected by temperature, pH levels, the growing conditions, and the sugar content. Moreover, we have varieties with seeds and seedless varieties. Seeded varieties may carry up to 4 seeds. Seeds contain tannins at a rate of 4-6%.

Generally, the grapevine life cycle has 2 phases, the Growing Period and the Dormancy period.

The growing period is separated into three stages:

- The first stage starts with sprouting and ends with blooming.
- The second stage starts with blooming and ends with veraison (change of color of grapes)
- The third stage starts with veraison and ends with maturing. During this stage, acidity normally decreases, while the content of sugars increases.

Dormancy starts right after leaf drop and ends with lacrimation (normally late autumn to winter – November to February). During this phase, vines rest. The plants do not perform any of their normal procedures. However, in the tropical zone, dormancy does not occur. Due to the fact that vines do not have to tolerate temperatures below 12 °C (53.6 °F), they escape this phase and the growing period may last up to 100-130 days.

Grapes are among the most famous summer fruits. People consume grapes for thousands of years, as the fruit has always been a key element of their nutrition. We can see grapes on ancient greek wall paintings, while at the same time we have historic reports referring to the significance of grapes and wine in Ancient Greeks' diet and lifestyle. Nowadays, people consume grapes and their products, not only for their flavor, but also for their significant nutritional value. Grapes, and hence wine, have various health beneficial components that may differ slightly depending on the variety and growing methods.

Health Benefits of Grape Consumption:

- Cardiovascular Benefits
- Fights against Cancer
- Promotes Skin Health
- Improves Digestion
- Anti Inflammatory Properties
- Eye Health Benefits
- Boosts the Immune System

- Potential Anti-Diabetic Action

According to the USDA, 100 gr of red seedless grapes include:

Energy: 65 kcal

Protein: 0.72g

Total lipid: 0.72g

Carbohydrate, by difference: 17.39g

Sugars, total: 16.67g

Fiber: 0.7g

Ca: 14mg

Fe: 0.26mg

Na: 0

Vitamin C: 10.9mg

Vitamin A IU: 72IU

Heart Health

Grapes, especially red varieties, contain a significant amount of polyphenols, such as resveratrol, which lower the risk of atherosclerosis and strokes. Those polyphenols are associated with lowering blood pressure and reducing the risk of cardiovascular disease.

Skin Health

Resveratrol is the main reason we see grapes appearing in cosmetic medicine. This powerful antioxidant protects cells collagen, helping the skin remain young and healthy.

Cancer

In the eternal fight against cancer, polyphenols such as resveratrol and quercetin once again play the most important role. According to studies, resveratrol may be able to prevent tumor growth in various organs, such as liver, skin, stomach, breast, skin, colon, and lymph. [Red wine](#) contains resveratrol which if consumed wisely, could have beneficial effects. However, consuming high quantities of wine could increase the risk of various heart and liver diseases.

Improves Digestion

Grapes are a source of fiber, which is known to boost the good functioning of the digestive system and may prevent constipation.

Vitamin C

Grapes are a great source of vitamin C, which promotes skin health and boosts our immune system.

Eye Health

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[Grapes](#) also contain antioxidants such as lutein and zeaxanthin, which neutralize free radicals and prevent eye-damaging conditions, like cataracts.

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